

Functional Form of Entropy Due to Physical Constraints? Part 3

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In Part 2, we argued that a key idea of a certain type of equilibrium (Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein) was to have a function $g(p(e_i))$ which acts like a probability (not necessarily $p(e_i)$ where e_i is single particle energy) such that $g(p(e_1))g(p(e_2)) = g(p(e_i)) g(p(e_j))$ for any $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$. In other words, this was introduced as a specific kind of loss of information which apparently corresponds to some physical scenarios. The function g is then determined by the physics of scattering. In such an approach, one may immediately find various distributions which ensure this equality of product $g(p(e_i))$ s for $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$ pairs. In particular, one then has: $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$. In Part 2, we argued that one could formally obtain such a $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$, by maximizing $g(p(e_i)) \ln(g(p(e_i)))$ (varying $g(p(e_i))$ subject to the constraints $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}_1$ and $\sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}_2$, i.e. $p(e_i)$ is mapped to $g(p(e_i))$ as in a dual space situation. This approach allows for any $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)/f(p(e_i))$ solution, i.e. there is no restriction on $f(p(e_i))$. We write $p(e_i)$ explicitly in $g(p(e_i))$ because it represents the probability for a particle with e_i to appear in the reaction. Thus, this is a specific scenario of solutions.

Here we are, however, also concerned with stability, i.e. change of $p(e_i)$ to $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ which physically occurs with fluctuations. Thus, we seek a function of $p(e_i)$ which ensures that $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$, but at the same time is stable to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. We find that stability requires for $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) / f(p(e_i))$ that $f(p(e_i))$ be linear in $p(e_i)$ which is associated with the two cases for fermions and bosons and no others. To achieve this result, however, in which variation is respect to the functional form of $p(e_i)$, we restrict the function to be varied to one which has statistical meaning. In particular, we find that one may have $f(p(e_i)) = (a+bp(e_i))^n$ power n , but that for the function to have statistical meaning, $n=1$.

Thus, the dual space approach used in Part 2 to find a distribution based on a $g(p(e_i))$ can be used for any $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) / f(p(e_i))$, but only an f linear in $p(e_i)$ is stable to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$ and associated with a statistical meaningful function, i.e. entropy. In other words, one does not only have the issue of certain loss of information (all $g(p(e_i))$, $g(p(e_i))$ products yield the same value for $e_i+e_j=\text{constant}$), but there also seems to be the situation of stability under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$. Thus, entropy seems to be an important function as it not only ensures that $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$, but also that there is stability under $p \rightarrow p+dp$, but we suggest that the entropy function must have statistical meaning (which we discuss below).

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Case and Generalizations

One may obtain the MB distribution directly from reaction balance for elastic collisions:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ with } e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j \text{ or } \ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ or } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1))$$

Reaction balance does not entail any check on $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ being stable to:

$$p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \quad ((2))$$

One may see that:

$$\ln(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) + dp(e_i)/p(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, $\ln(p(e_i))$ is not stable to $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, but one may readily see that:

$$p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((4)) \text{ is.}$$

We further note that ((4)) is not some arbitrary function, but is the average value of $\ln(p(e_i))$ where $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. Thus, it is a statistical meaningful function which ensures both $\ln(g) = -e_i/T$ and stability under $p \rightarrow p + dp$.

We next consider the more general situation of:

$$p(e_i) / f(p(e_i)) \quad ((5))$$

In such a case, $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)/f(p(e_i))$ is like a new probability which governs collisions. At the same time, it consists of two kinds of probabilities. $p(e_i)$ is the probability to have a particle with e_i , and $f(p(e_i))$ is an enhancement/hindrance kind of probability (even if not normalized).

We first seek a loss of information if $g(p(e_i))$ if products of $g(p(e_i))$ are the same for any $e_i + e_j =$ constant pairs. In Part 2, we argued that one could formally map $p(e_i)$ to $g(p(e_i))$, i.e. create a dual space and also map the constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{eave} \quad ((6)) \text{ to}$$

$$\sum_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number1} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number2}. \quad ((7))$$

In such a case, one could define:

$$\sum_i g(p(e_i)) h(g(p(e_i))) \quad ((8))$$

such that its differential with respect to g yields a linear combination of the differentials of the mapped constraints ((7)). This would then yield:

$$dg h(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T dg \quad \text{and} \quad g dh/dg = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad h = \ln(g(p(e_i))) \quad ((10))$$

$$((10)) \text{ then yields: } g(p(e_i)) = \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((11))$$

In such a scenario, one may use any function $f(p(e_i))$ to obtain a distribution. There is no notion of stability under $p \rightarrow p + dp$ here.

The Case of Stability

We are concerned in this note, however, with stability under ((2)), something that was not considered in Part 2. For the MB case, it did not appear at the:

$h(g(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((12)) level, where $h = \ln$

and one is forced to create the function $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ that is stable under ((2))

If one insists on stability occurring one may consider:

$\ln(g(p(e_i))) = \ln(p(e_i)/f(p(e_i)))$ ((13)) level, then:

$\ln((p+dp) / (f(p+dp))) = \ln(p) - \ln(f) + dp/p - df/dp/f dp$ ((14))

A solution is $d\ln(f)/dp = 1/p$, i.e. $f=p$ which is not useful. It seems that like in the MB case, one needs to consider multiplying by factor functions. For $\ln(p)$ one multiplied by $p+dp$ in the MB case, which should carry over here because $f=1$ should yield the MB result. In fact, it becomes evident that one need not retain the form $\ln(p/f)$ at all even though $g(p(e_i)) = p/f(p)$. Rather, one may create a function which splits $\ln(p)$ and $\ln(f)$ as it is already known that $p \ln(p)$ does in the MB, $f=1$ case.

Ultimately, one wants the result:

$\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ to emerge, but it must follow from using ((2))

This seems to impose restrictions on the form of $f(p(e_i))$. In other words, any $f(p(e_i))$ can be used with the dual approach of Part 2 to find a distribution, but only a linear $f(p)$ in p can be used to create a function of $p(e_i)$ which under ((2)) yields $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$. In other words, it is possible that in nature there is something more than the loss of information about $e_i+e_j=\text{constant}$ pairs ($g(p(e_i))*g(p(e_j))$ being the same for all $e_i+e_j=\text{constant}$ pairs). It seems that one must also have stability under ((2)). This ultimately leads to two unique linear in p forms of $f(p)$, one applying to fermions and the other to bosons. To see this consider:

$(p+dp) \ln(p + dp) \rightarrow p \ln(p) + dp \ln(p) + dp$ ((15))

If $\ln(p/f) = -e/T$, then the constraint $\sum_i e_i dp = 0$ should be used. This suggests that one requires a $dp \ln(f)$ term.

Consider $(q+dq/dp dp) (-\ln(f) - df/dp/f dp) \rightarrow -q\ln(f) + dq/dp dp (-\ln f) + \text{other terms}$

One requires that $q = p$ and $dq/dp = 1$. Thus, q is a linear function of p .

Due to $\sum_i dp(e_i)=0$, the sum of the dp term in ((15)) is 0. Thus, one must consider:

$-qdf/dp/f$ dp as summing to 0 (or another constant). This suggests that:

f is linear in p and $q=f$ as a possible solution. One has to make use of the Sum over i $dp(e_i) = 0$ constraint because there is no reason to expect that f alone is linked to e_i/T . Formally:

constant/ $q = d/dp \ln(f)$ where q is a linear function in p ((16))

If $f=(a+bp)$ power n ((17)) with $q=a+bp$ then one has a solution.

Thus, not any $f(p)$ is allowed, but a family of solutions seems to exist.

The question then becomes: Is this function of p which is stable under $p \rightarrow p + dp$ completely arbitrary? If it is, then one has solutions for any power of n . If on the other hand, the function must have some statistical meaning as well, one may see that:

Sum over i $p \ln(p)$ is the average of $\ln(p)$ ((17)).

In such a case, both p and $f(p)$ act like independent probabilities in an action-reaction balance equation. " p ": is the probability for a particle with e_i to be present to react, but $f(p)$ is an enhancement or hindrance of the reaction. Both behave as AND probabilities. Thus, it seems that one must choose:

$n=1$ if one wishes to have $\pm q(p) \ln(f(p))$ represent an average of $f(p)$ with $f(p)=q(p)$ ((18))

Otherwise, one has a constant times the average which does not follow the pattern of $p \ln(p)$. As a result, it seems that there may be some meaning to the function of p which is stable to $p \rightarrow p + dp$, but at the same time yields $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$. This function is called entropy and thus seems to have some physical relevance beyond the idea of $g(p(e_i))$ products of e_i, e_j pairs such that $e_i + e_j = \text{constant}$ having the same value. There seem to be two ideas at work at least in the MB, FD and BE cases. The idea of e_i, e_j pairs with the same sum having the same $g(p(e_i))$ product and the idea of stability under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ which introduces a function (called entropy) which is not arbitrary, but is represents a linear combination of average informations where there may be more than $p(e_i)$ acting as a probability. In the FD and BE cases, this forces f in $p(e_i)/f(p(e_i))$ to be linear in $p(e_i)$.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

We have suggested that we require $f(p) = a+bp$. It seems, however, that $b=\pm 1$ as one may create:

-1* Entropy density = $p \ln(p) + (1-p) \ln(1-p)$ (fermions)

-1*Entropy density = $p \ln(p) - (1+p) \ln(1+p)$ (bosons)

It seems that "a" is a free constant, but for physical reasons takes on the value of 1 in the FD and BE cases.

Physical Meaning of $p \rightarrow p+dp$

In this note, we focus on a second condition beyond $g(p(e_i)) g(p(e_j)) = \text{constant}_1$ for $e_i+e_j=\text{constant}_2$, namely that one have a function which yields this result, i.e. $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$, but at the same time is stable with respect to $p \rightarrow p+dp$. The question is: Why is this stability needed? We argue that in a given system at equilibrium, one may have fluctuations in $p(e_i)$. These fluctuations should leave the system stable to first order we argue if one has an equilibrium. This is similar to mechanical perturbations for a stable equilibrium, i.e. a particle at the bottom of a potential for which a change dx in x leads to $V(x) \rightarrow \text{constant} + dx(dx) b$, i.e. oscillatory behaviour (i.e. a stable equilibrium).

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 2, we consider a dual space in which $p(e_i)$ maps to $g(p(e_i))$, where g is a known function due to the physics of collisions. In fact, we model it as $g(p) = p / f(p)$. We also mapped the two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{eave}$ to $\sum_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}_1$ and $\sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \text{number}_2$. This leads to $\ln(p/f(p)) = -e/T$ for any function $f(p)$ and introduces the feature that $g(p(e_i))g(p(e_j)) = \text{constant}_1$ for any $e_i+e_j=\text{constant}_2$.

Here we argue that we wish to retain these features, but want to have stability under $p \rightarrow p+dp$. We seek a function of p which is stable under this change, but yields $\ln(p/f(p)) = -e_i/T$. We note that such a function is $p \ln(p)$ for $f=1$. We then try to show that a general solution is $f=a+bp$ where $a=1, b=\pm 1$. In other words, only special $f(p)$ values (linked to the Fermi Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases) allow for this stability. We argue that there are two key features $\ln(g(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ and stability under $p \rightarrow p+dp$ and that it is the entropy which allows for both.

Action-reaction balance is useful in establishing the first property, but would allow for any $p/f(p)=g(p(e_i))$, but does not ensure stability. Thus, entropy seems to be essential for ensuring stability.